

DEVELOPMENT OF A COMPOSITE FLOOR PANEL TO REPLACE PLYWOOD FLOORING IN RAIL CAR INTERIORS

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SUMMARY: This paper describes the development of a lightweight composite panel which offers an alternative to conventional plywood flooring. The composite panel has the potential to substantially increase, and possibly eliminate, the re-flooring interval for rail car interiors.

The composite floor panel is economically competitive with the plywood and although the basic panel unit price is presently higher than plywood, there are potential savings in the installation, and significant savings if the through life costs are considered. Further, the long term trend in plywood price is likely to be upward as environmental considerations become more influential, (such as the restrictions placed on the import of tropical hardwood species). In contrast the composite panel price is likely to remain stable.

The panel skins and structural core are fabricated from fibre-reinforced phenolic resin. The foam fill is also phenolic. With phenolic resin used throughout the panel fire resistance is of a very high order. For floor applications the panel are made flat though curved panels for other applications are being considered. The composite panel is designed as an alternative to treated F14 stress grade structural plywood but outperforms the plywood in nearly all aspects.

The testing and evaluation of the composite floor panel are described and the various performance criteria are discussed.

KEYWORDS: phenolic panel, treated plywood, rail car floors

INTRODUCTION

Passenger rail cars in New South Wales have conventionally used treated plywood flooring. The plywood deteriorates due to the effects of water ingress and wear, and has to be replaced at regular intervals (generally between five and fifteen years depending on location within the car). The cost of rail car refurbishment involving floor replacements is high. Furthermore the availability of treated plywood of adequate quality is declining. The only Australian based manufacturer of treated plywood closed its plant in 1996. Hence an alternative flooring product is sought.

A 13mm phenolic Composite Floor Panel was developed as a direct replacement option for the 13 mm treated plywood used by the State Rail Authority of New South Wales (SRA) in its double-deck passenger rail car fleet.

The panel configuration was designed to suit this particular application but other configurations are possible.

The composite floor panels are of sandwich construction having skins of glass fibre reinforced phenolic resin, and a core consisting of glass fibre reinforced phenolic and phenolic foam. This construction provides good structural and sound attenuation properties with low panel weight and cost.

PHENOLIC COMPOSITES

Glass fibre reinforced plastics (GRP) are well established materials of construction for rail car interiors in Australia being extensively used for internal linings, luggage compartments, stairs, seating etc. These components have traditionally been manufactured from glass fibre reinforced polyester or modified acrylic resin.

The 'resol' version of phenolic resins is designed to be processed like conventional polyester resin commonly used in fibre reinforced plastics.

The advantage of phenolic resin is its outstanding heat resistance and fire performance which has been widely reported in the literature eg Gibson et al [1].

The physical and mechanical properties of the phenolic based composites, as reported by Forsdyke et al, [2] O'Brart, [3] and others, are in most cases comparable to polyester based composites with the notable exceptions of elongation, colour and surface appearance- which are generally inferior to other thermoset polymers. Phenolic composites usually require either painting or a decorative coating if good aesthetics are required for the application. Rail car flooring however is usually finished with a vinyl mat wear surface and hence an aesthetic finish is not required of the floor panel itself.

As reported by Forsdyke [4], Brown [5] and others, worldwide use of phenolic composites is growing and examples of industries using phenolic composites are the automotive, rail, aircraft, marine, offshore and building and construction. Applications in the rail industry to date include: cable supports and enclosures; live rail covers; various signal, aerial and switchgear enclosures; interior panels (with decorative coatings); luggage compartments; sleeper car partitions; diesel engine heat shields; underground station tunnel linings, and rail car flooring. Several recent developments have involved the manufacture of complete rail cars or freight wagons of composite material using filament winding, resin infusion or pultrusion. An example using pultruded carbon fibre is reported by Suzuki and Satoh [6].

SELECTION OF FLOOR PANEL CONFIGURATION

A number of panel configurations were initially considered including: steel faced plywood; aluminium faced plywood; aluminium faced pvc foam sandwich; composite faced pvc foam sandwich; aluminium or composite faced honeycomb core sandwich, 3-D distance fabric, and lastly, a sandwich construction using a moulded composite core with composite skins.

The last of these options was selected with phenolic composite chosen in preference to aluminium for both core and skins as it was considered to have better fire performance,

fatigue resistance, and potentially better corrosion resistance (reports from the rail car manufacturer indicated corrosion of aluminium in wet areas and insulation from the stainless steel structural members would be an additional requirement). The bonding of aluminium was also considered to be a major issue which could be largely avoided by using the composite option.

The plywood core options were rejected due in part to the problems experienced by the SRA and reported by the rail car manufacturer caused by water ingress (for example the stainless steel faced plywood suffered from delamination) and also due to anticipated future availability problems of good quality plywood.

The pvc foam core option was rejected on the basis of poor heat resistance and fire performance. If an aluminium faced pvc core sandwich construction were used then under fire or local overheating conditions rapid heat transmission through the aluminium to the core would lead to rapid deterioration of floor integrity.

Honeycomb core options were considered but rejected on grounds of high cost, poor availability, and on process considerations. They are however considered to have the highest ratio of stiffness-to-weight hence their widespread use in aerospace.

3-D 'distance fabrics' with phenolic matrix and foam filling appeared to offer most of the desired properties but were rejected on grounds of cost and limitations (at the time) on available dimensions and lay-up.

Attention therefore became focussed on the all composite moulded core sandwich construction as it had the most attractive combination of features from performance, cost and manufacturing considerations. The last of these, the manufacturing process, proved to be crucial.

MANUFACTURING PROCESS

With the raw material cost of the composite approaching the finished plywood panel cost, it was necessary to develop a cost effective and yet versatile, high throughput process. Existing processes that meet this description include pultrusion, the continuous laminating/sandwich panel process, and to a lesser extent, resin transfer moulding (RTM) . However none of these processes are capable of producing a hollowed cored product with the combination of section intricacy, low wall thickness, and panel width variation required for this application. A completely new process was therefore developed with the assistance of an Australian Federal Government grant.

The panel making process is sufficiently versatile to allow a wide range of lay-ups to be used for moulded corrugated core and the panel skins. Most common forms of fibre reinforcement can be used including woven and random mats, stitched, knitted and low crimp fabrics, and tissues or veils. The process allows the option of incorporating foam within the core channels. The foam filling can be complete (ie in all cavities of the corrugated core), or optionally in a portion of the core such as in alternate cavities. The incorporation of foam increases thermal insulation, acoustic attenuation, and panel compressive properties. For the floor application a phenolic foam was selected as this has good heat and fire resistance. The mechanical properties of phenolic foam are generally poor. However when incorporated into

the cavities of the corrugated core, the foam contributes to the panel compressive properties as compressive load puts the foam into partial hydrostatic compression due to its encapsulation.

The panel does not depend on the foam for its bending resistance which it derives from the corrugated composite core acting in combination with the skins.

Although one particular configuration was selected for the rail floor application, the process is sufficiently versatile to allow for many other configurations to suit other applications. A light-weight version of the panel without foam core can be used for fire resistant partitioning for example.

PANEL TESTING AND EVALUATION

Panel Load-Deflection Testing

To assess the panels suitability for the rail floor applications, a number of tests were carried out. The first set of tests included three point bending (Fig.1) to assess panel static stiffness and strength, and repeated three-point-bending (ie cyclic testing- Fig. 3)to assess retention of integrity with repeated loading. The test method was provided by the rail car manufacturer and prime contractor for refurbishment as 'Goninan Test Specification Ref. 0510E/3 parts 1 & 2'.

Fig. 1: Typical three-point-bend test

Fig. 2: Load-Deflection Curves for Composite and Plywood Panels

Typical load deflection curves for the composite and the plywood are shown in Figure 2. In all cases the composite panel has a higher load at failure than the plywood and the lowest value for the composite panel is 15% higher than the highest value for plywood. The mean value for the composite is 80% higher than the mean value for the plywood. The variation for both panels at this stage was quite high as the early panels were largely hand made. Since the testing of the early panels, the variation for the composite panel has been reduced with samples produced on the full scale pilot plant and further improvement is anticipated as refinements are made to the manufacturing process.

As well as the load to failure being higher for the composite panel than for the plywood panel, the mode of failure is considered to be safer for the composite panel. The plywood panel fails by tensile rupture of the plies starting from the underside of the panel. The residual load carrying capability is effectively zero. For the composite panel however, initial failure is by compression in the top skin with the lower skin remaining intact and capable of carrying load after initial failure. Composite panel samples will typically sustain a subsequent load of over 40% of the initial failure load, when simply supported- more with end fixity or continuity.

Panel Cyclic Load Testing

As the composite panel consists of a laminated construction it was considered necessary to subject samples to a cyclic load to assess whether or not the panel would de-laminate or deteriorate in anyway. The set-up for cyclic loading is similar to that for the static load-deflection test ie three-point-bending, but with the load applied and released in a sinusoidal fashion. The test rig is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Cyclic Load Test Arrangement

Fig. 4a: Typical results of load-deflection tests (a) after cyclic loading to 10^5 cycles with 4.5 mm central deflection (b) after cyclic loading to 10^7 cycles with 2.0 mm central deflection

The results of initial testing (ie to ‘Goninan Test Specification Ref. 0510E/3 part 2’) showed that no deterioration in panel stiffness or load carrying ability due to the cyclic loading called for in the test method was detected, despite the deflection of 4.5 mm being over twice that considered to be the maximum in service deflection ie 2 mm (Fig. 4a). It was therefore decided to test a sample for a much higher number of cycles ie 10^7 to a maximum deflection of 2mm. After this test the panel was loaded to failure and again showed no significant reduction in stiffness or load carrying ability (Fig. 4b). These results were re-assuring as it was not known at the outset of this development whether or not a laminated phenolic composite panel with corrugated core would suffer delamination between core and skins as a result of repeated flexural loading, considering that contact area between core and skin is less than 50% of the panel area.

The fatigue behaviour of uni-directional glass fibre reinforced phenolic composites is reported by Branco et al [7], including the effects of varying fibre volume fraction, fibre surface treatment and stress ratio. Their conclusions suggest that while the fatigue life of a phenolic matrix composite is less that of one based on epoxy, 10^7 load cycles can be comfortably exceeded if the normalised stress is below 20 %. The different fibre surface treatments used appear to have minor influence on the reported fatigue life.

High Heel Shoe Puncture Test

As train floors can be subjected to potentially damaging effects of high heel shoe loads, a test was undertaken using a 5mm cylindrical steel impressor (contact area 0.2 cm²) to compare the puncture resistance of the composite panel with the plywood. The set-up is shown in Figure 5.

Fig 5: High Heel Puncture Test

The minimum puncture load for the composite panel was 2.31 kN (11.8 kN / cm²) which compares with a maximum value for the plywood of 1.62 kN (8.25 kN/cm²) thus representing an increase in puncture resistance of 42%. When this test was repeated placing a piece of vinyl floor covering on the panel sample, the covering became permanently marked at approximately 0.8 kN load.

Voerpost [8], considering the potential suitability of 3-D distance fabrics for rail flooring applications, reports that a typical heel loading requirement in Europe would be 150 kgf over 1 cm² (1.5 kN/cm²). This requirement is easily met by the composite floor panel, but a typical foam filled 3-D distance fabric is likely to require additional layers of reinforcement on the upper skin.

Drop Weight Impact Testing

A search for a standard impact test relevant to this type of application was unsuccessful- the ASTM method for roof panels and the drop weight 'tup' test were not considered appropriate. A simple test to assess the tolerance of the composite panel to incidental impact damage and comparing the outcome with that for plywood was devised. The test consisted of dropping a 6.7 kg steel sphere from increasing heights of 1.0 m, 1.5m and 2.0m at different locations. The arrangement is shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Drop Weight Impact Test Arrangement

For the composite panel, no visible damage occurred in each case. For the plywood panel cracks appeared on the underside of the panel. Three-point-bend test specimens were subsequently cut from the impacted panels for residual strength testing. In this test the maximum load recorded for the plywood specimen was 1.8 kN before panel collapse compared with 5.4 kN for the composite panel which failed in compression of the upper skin (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7- Load-deflection tests after drop weight impact- (a) plywood (b) composite
Note: different axes scales

This test suggests that the damage tolerance to this type of impact of the composite panel is superior to that of the plywood which failed on the more critical (tensile) underside.

Fire Testing

Nine panel samples 600mm x 450mm were submitted to the Australian Wool Testing Authority (AWTA) for testing to Australian Standard AS 1530.3 'Simultaneous determination of ignitability, flame propagation, heat release and smoke release'. This test is a radiant panel fire test similar to other national standards such as ASTM E 162, BS 476 Pt 6 & 7, DIN 4102, NFP92-501 etc.

The result was given as indices 0,0,0,0-1 which is the best result possible for the test, thus confirming the excellent early fire resistance of glass fibre reinforced composites as reported by others.

Sound Transmission Testing

Samples of plywood (16 mm and 13 mm thickness) and composite panels (13 mm thickness), of plan area 610 mm x 610 mm were tested for sound transmission loss. Of the two composite panels tested one was 100 % foam filled while the other had no foam filling. The wideband (63- 10,000 Hz) sound transmission loss values recorded were as per Table 1.

Table 1: Wideband sound transmission loss values for ply and composite panels

16 mm Plywood	13 mm Plywood	13 mm Composite (no foam)	13 mm Composite (100 % foam)
TL = 30 dB	TL = 24 dB	TL = 23 dB	TL = 26 dB

The results indicate that the sound transmission loss for the composite panels is of the same order as for the plywood and that foam filling has the effect of increasing sound transmission loss.

Panel Installation

As main bearers in the SRA's rail cars run transversely, the composite floor panels are made in typical lengths of 5 m and with widths from 0.6 m to 1.4 m depending on location within the car. The panel edges are supported on secondary bearers which run longitudinally. Two fixing methods have been evaluated (1) self tapping screw fasteners and (2) adhesive bonding. A composite panel sample with each fixing method was subjected to the cyclic load test described above in both dry and wet conditions. No noticeable deterioration of the panel or its fixing occurred and the panels with screw fixing gave the highest residual load-to failure after cyclic loading to 10^7 cycles with 2 mm central deflection. Both fixing methods would appear to be suitable for the application. The screw fasteners used in the testing were an 'off-the-shelf' type with a shallow counter-sunk head as the skin of the composite panel is thin. Subsequently a dedicated fastener was made to specification to suit the application.

Service Trials

For trial and evaluation of the product the SRA gave permission for a double-deck car to be fitted with the composite floor panel during scheduled refurbishment. At the time of writing this car has been in service for approximately eighteen months with no problems reported after periodic inspections.

CONCLUSIONS

A plywood replacement floor panel was developed along with an novel manufacturing process for economic volume production. The replacement product was constructed of glass fibre reinforced phenolic resin and whilst of the same weight as the plywood, appears to have superior structural properties as determined by the evaluation tests described above.

Whilst the composite product is likely to be more expensive than the traditional treated plywood it replaces, it is of similar order of cost so as to minimise the impact on operating costs.

There is scope for further product development with improvements in structural properties anticipated together with the potential for reducing weight.

The product concept has potential for use in other applications. A design model is currently under development for this purpose. Material coupon test data will be incorporated in the model which is based on laminate analysis. The model will incorporate failure modes and be verified against test results on full scale panels.

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